

From Evidence to Action: Improving Nutrition Support for Cancer Survivors

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Cancer survivorship is increasing globally due to advances in detection and treatment, creating a growing population with complex long-term health needs. Nutrition plays a key role in improving quality of life, reducing recurrence risk and managing comorbidities. However, despite strong evidence linking diet, body composition and metabolic health with survivorship outcomes, access to consistent, evidence-based nutrition care remains limited. This policy brief aims to highlight the gap between evidence and practice in nutrition for cancer survivors, identify key barriers within healthcare systems and propose strategies to integrate nutrition more effectively into survivorship care pathways.

Research Findings

The research highlights that while nutrition significantly influences survivorship outcomes, there is substantial inconsistency in guidance, access and delivery of nutrition care. Survivors frequently experience long-term effects such as fatigue, metabolic dysfunction and cardiovascular risk, which can be improved through appropriate dietary support. However, nutrition is often not systematically embedded within oncology services, and access to dietetic support varies widely. Evidence-based interventions exist but are not consistently implemented, reflecting a clear evidence–practice gap. A tiered model of nutrition care is proposed for integration into current healthcare systems.

Policy Implications

Policymakers should prioritise the integration of nutrition into cancer survivorship care as a standard component of treatment pathways. This includes investing in dietetic workforce capacity, embedding nutrition screening and support across oncology services and ensuring equitable access to evidence-based interventions. Standardised guidelines and care models are needed to reduce variability in practice and improve outcomes. Policy should also support multidisciplinary approaches and long-term follow-up, recognising survivorship as an ongoing phase of care rather than an endpoint. Strengthening health systems to deliver consistent nutrition care could reduce healthcare burden and improve quality of life for survivors.

Industry Recommendations

The National Cancer Control Programme, working with the Health Service Executive, should strengthen the integration of nutrition within cancer survivorship models of care. This includes embedding routine nutrition screening and referral pathways within oncology services, and expanding access to specialist oncology dietitians across acute and community settings. Standardised, evidence-based patient education resources should be developed to support self-management. Investment in digital health and telehealth dietetic services can enhance access and continuity, particularly in underserved areas. A coordinated, multidisciplinary approach is required to ensure consistent implementation of nutrition care across the cancer continuum in Ireland.

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Further Reading:

Keaver, L., O’Callaghan, N.,
Johnston, K. E. & Cushen, S. J.
(2026) Nutrition in cancer
survivorship: bridging the
evidence-practice gap.
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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Life Sciences, Medtech &
Medical Devices

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG): 3. Good Health and Well-Being

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